

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

September 18, 2025
LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

Co-funded by
the European Union

LOGOS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE

September, 2025

EDITORS

Valbona NATHANAILI
Logos University College

Elona KARAFILI
Polis University

Blerta DRENOFCI (CANI)
Logos University College

Konstantinos GIAKOUMIS
Logos University College

Dužanka BOŠKOVIĆ
University of Sarajevo

Arbana KADRIU
South East European University

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an initiative of LOGOS University College, supported by the consortium
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Address: Rr: “Dritan Hoxha”, Tiranë.

valbona.nathanaili@kulogos.edu.al

www.kulogos.edu.al

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CONTENTS

ABOUT THE EDITORS.....	5
Welcome Speech:	
FOSTERING INNOVATION AND ADVANCING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION.....	8
PROF. ILIA NINKA, RECTOR	
DIGITALIZATION AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE LABOR MARKET.....	9
MRS. GERTIOLA CEPANI	
ADDRESSING THE DIGITAL LEAP IN THE WESTERN BALKANS Preliminary impact exposition of the HOMO DIGITALIS Erasmus+ CBHE Project.....	10
PROF. KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUMIS	
THE STRATEGIC ACTIONS FOR AI IN HIGHER EDUCATION.....	12
EMERITUS PROFESSOR, NIKOLAOS AVOURIS	
SUMMARY OF ACTIVITES.....	16
PART ONE: DIGITAL COMPETENCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE LABOUR MARKET.....	19
(1) THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT CASE STUDY: ALBANIAN UNIVERSITIES DURING THE PANDEMIC PERIOD.....	21
EMIRA SPAHAJ, EDISELA MENA, MALVINA HYSA, BLERTA AVDIA	
(2) BARRIERS AND OPPORTUNITIES IN ALBANIAN HIGHER EDUCATION FOR STUDENTS WITH DISABILITIES. A MIXED-METHODS ANALYSIS.....	37
BLERTA DRENOFCI (ÇANI), VALBONA NATHANAILI	
(3) THE DIGITAL EMPLOYMENT GAP IN ALBANIA Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education.....	61
GERTJANA HASALLA	
PART TWO: INSTITUTIONAL STRATEGIES AND POLICY DEVELOPMENT.....	75
(4) INTEGRATED TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT AND RESTORATION STRATEGY FOR THE ‘TOPULLI’ HOUSE Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies.....	77
NIKOLLA VESHO, PANAGIOTIS KYRATISIS, AJLA GJOKA, LUMTURI HASKA, SARA CIBA, MIGENA GJONI, ARDIS DUKA, ROMIR MAZARI	

(5)	THE ROLE OF MOOCS AND OPEN EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN HIGHER EDUCATION Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	101
	DORINA MINXURI	
(6)	LANGUAGE TECHNOLOGIES AND DIGITAL HUMANITIES FOR LOW-RESOURCE LANGUAGES AND COMMUNITIES.....	113
	ARBANA KADRIU, LEJLA ABAZI-BEXHETI	
(7)	THE COGNITIVE-DIGITAL TURN IN HIGHER EDUCATION A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio.....	125
	FULVIO PAPADHOPULLI, MEGI TAF AJ	
(8)	DEFINING A STRATEGIC ACTION PLAN FOR AI IN HIGHER EDUCATION.....	141
	NIKOLAOS AVOURIS	
(9)	INSTITUTIONAL POLICIES AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR ADVANCING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION.....	153
	HAJDIN BERISHA, AGRON HAJDARI, BEKIM SAMADRAXHA	
PART THREE: THE INTENDED AND ATTAINED CURRICULUM.....		155
(10)	DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN SOCIAL SCIENCES – A PILOT STUDY From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project	157
	VALBONA NATHANAILI, BLERTA DRENOFCI (ÇANI), KONSTANTINOS GIAKOU MIS, DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ, ARBANA KADRIU, ANISA DUKA	
(11)	ENHANCING LEARNING THROUGH MULTIMEDIA CULTURAL HERITAGE APPLICATIONS Managing Cognitive Load.....	177
	MERIMA MUSLIĆ, DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ, VENSADA OKANOVIĆ, SELMA RIZVIĆ	
(12)	INTEGRATING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES INTO HIGHER EDUCATION CURRICULA A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the HOMO DIGITALIS Project	193
	JUNA MUÇA, ANXHELA LASKA, ELPINIQI MERKURI, EDVALDO BEGOTARAJ	
CONFERENCE SUMMARY AND REFLECTIONS.....		209
	VALBONA NATHANAILI	
INDEX OF AUTHORS AND PAPER NUMBERS		211

VALBONA NATHANAILI

LOGOS University College

Dr. Nathanaili is currently a lecturer and researcher in the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania, with an experience of more than 35 years in the field of academia and publication. She is a Bachelor in physics and a doctoral degree holders in the science of pedagogy, both from University of Tirana. Major areas of research over the last few years are the politics and reforms in Albanian Education System, methodology of teaching science, university pedagogy, the future of schooling and Recognition and Accreditation of Prior Learning gained after flexible learning paths. She is analyst, writers and contributor for different periodic Albanian newspaper and television outlets. Nathanaili, in collaboration with different HEIs, has been initiator and supporter of STEM national campaigns, to encourage girls to pursue careers in science, technology, engineering and math fields and promote women in those fields. Dr. Nathanaili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects.

KONSTANTINOS GIAKOUIMIS

LOGOS University College

Konstantinos Giakoumis is Professor of History, Arts and Didactics at LOGOS University College, where he also leads the Faculty of Humanities and Linguistic Communication. He is a doctoral degree (Ph.D.) holder PhD from the University of Birmingham, serves on the international advisory board of Art Readings (Institute of Art Studies, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences) and reviews for the Serbian Academy of Sciences, the University of Crete, and international journals including *Speculum* (University of Chicago Press), the *Journal of Religious History* (Wiley), and *Politics, Religion & Ideology* (Taylor & Francis). He has also served as coordinator of a number of ERASMUS+ CBHE projects (Roaming, Homo Digitalis, DiLanEdu-WB). For a Marie Curie fellowship application in 2018 he received the European Commission's Seal of Excellence. A prolific scholar, his work appears in leading journals such as *Byzantine and Modern Greek Studies* (Cambridge), *Turkish Historical Review* (Brill), and the *International Journal of Cultural Policy* (Taylor & Francis). His most recent book examines the Codex of the Diocese/Metropolis of Dryinoupolis and Gjirokastra (1760–1858), published by LOGOS University College Press.

ELONA KARAFILI

POLIS University

Dr. Elona Karafili is an expert in the field of economic development. She is a lecturer and researcher at POLIS University, Tirana, Albania since 2007. She holds a PhD in Urban Planning from Ferrara University and Polis University. Elona currently holds the position of the Deputy Rector of POLIS University. Her main topics of interest and expertise

include regional economic development and territorial competitiveness, which she has explored through a number of projects that focus on place-based innovation. Dr. Karafili has extensive experience in designing and directing research and capacity building projects. She is enthusiastic to strengthen the innovation ecosystem in Albania through fostering co-creative processes, academia–business collaboration and knowledge transfer, startup support and commercialization of research.

DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIĆ

University of Sarajevo

Vice Rector for Quality at the University of Sarajevo and a Professor at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering. Her research interests and teaching are focused on software engineering in biomedical and cognitive domains. She is highly motivated to learn about problem domains and committed to achieving a high level of user experience. In addition to teaching and research, she is engaged in various activities aimed at improving education in Bosnia and Herzegovina, especially through promoting student-centered and outcome-based learning and using software as educational content.

BLERTA DRENOFCI (CANI)

LOGOS University College

Dr. Drenofci has devoted her efforts for last 20 years at the Albanian Disability Rights Foundation, to the activities in advocacy and lobbying for disability related policy and legislation adoption and implementation and offering of supportive services for people in need throughout the country. She is an expert in the area of social policies and collaborator in the formulation of policy framework for people with disabilities in Albania. She has directed ADRF contribution in several important legal initiatives. ADRF is acknowledged as the pioneer and leader of human rights-based approach to disability and it is one in the few organizations that offer models of supportive services like mobility means, supported employment, free legal aid for people in need in Albania. Blerta has an PhD in Social Sciences and has an academic background, being a teacher of University of Tirana since 2013. She has been the leader and the author of a lot of studies in the field of social policies in and outside the country. She has been involved as a consultant in the research and policy development by several international agencies. During the years 2014-2022, she has been involved in the development of the new reform for the assessment of disability in Albania, based on international standards.

ARBANA KADRIU

South East European University

Arbana Kadriu is a Full Professor of Computer Science at the Faculty of Contemporary Sciences and Technologies, South East European University (SEEU) in Tetovo, North Macedonia. She earned her PhD in Computer Science from Ss. Cyril and Methodius

University, Skopje (2008), specializing in natural language processing and information retrieval. Her research spans AI and machine learning, software engineering, web information retrieval, social network analysis, and e-learning, with a growing focus on speech technologies for low-resource languages. Prof. Kadriu teaches across undergraduate, master's, and doctoral programs, organized into three clusters: Data & Intelligence, Software & the Web, and Research & Methods. She has supervised numerous master's and PhD theses in areas such as data mining–driven decision support, Albanian speech recognition, authorship analysis, and automatic music generation. Prof. Kadriu has authored 70+ publications across journals and international conferences (IEEE, Springer, PLOS ONE, and others) and contributes to international projects, including Erasmus+ initiatives on digital humanities and quality assurance, as well as COST actions on language technology and language learning.

PROCEEDINGS OF INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

TRENDS, CHALLENGES AND PERSPECTIVES

SEPTEMBER 18, 2025

Hosted by LOGOS University College

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- University of Patras
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LOGOS University College

SUMMARY OF ACTIVITIES

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Trends, Challenges and Perspectives

Logos University College, Tirana, Albania

Thursday, September 18, 2025

9.00-9.30	Registration
9.30-10.00	Open remarks
	Ilia Ninka, rector, LOGOS University College
	Gertiola Cepani, Director of Labour Market Services at 'National Employment and Skills Agency'
	Konstantinos Giakoumis, HOMO DIGITALIS Project Coordinator

TOPIC

AUTHOR(S)

OPPONENT

FIRST CONFERENCE TRACK			
Digital Competences in Higher Education and the Labour Market			
10.00-10.20	1. The Impact of Digital Transformation on Human Resource Management. Case Study: Albanian Universities During the Pandemic Period	Emira Spahaj, Edisela Mena, Malvina Hysa, Blerta Avdia	Elona Karafli
10.20-10.40	2. Barriers and Opportunities in Albanian Higher Education for Students with Disabilities: A Mixed-Methods Analysis	Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Valbona Nathaniaili	Merima Muslić
10.40-11.00	3. The Digital Employment Gap in Albania: Challenges and Strategies for Higher Education	Gertjana Hasalla	Arberore Bicaj
SECOND CONFERENCE TRACK			
Institutional Strategies and Policy Development			
11.00-11.20	4. Integrated Technical Assessment and Restoration Strategy for the "Topulli" House: Restoration Strategies, Revitalization Pathways and Advanced Digital Technologies	Nikolla Vesho, Panagiotis Kyriatsis, Ajla Gjoka, Lumturi Haska, Sara Ciba, Migena Gjoni, Ardis Duka, Romir Mazari	Konstantinos Giakoumis
11.20-11.40	5. The Role of MOOCs and Open Educational Resources in Higher Education: Applications in Teaching Medicine and Laboratory Science	Dorina Minxuri	Valbona Nathaniaili

11.40 -12.00	6. Language Technologies and Digital Humanities for Low-Resource Languages and Communities	Arbana Kadriu, Lejla Abazi-Bexheti	Blerta Drenofci (Çani)
12.00-12.20	Coffee break		
12.20-12.40	7. The Cognitive–Digital Turn in Higher Education. <i>A Longitudinal Analysis of AI Engagement in an Architectural Design Studio</i>	Fulvio Papadhopulli, Megi Tafaj	Nikolaos Avouris
12.40-13.00	8. Defining a Strategic Action Plan for AI in Higher Education	Nikolaos Avouris	Valbona Nathaniai
13.00-13.20	9. Institutional Policies and Strategic Directions for Advancing Digital Competencies in Higher Education	Hajdin Berisha, Agron Hajdari, Bekim Samadraxha	Flora Krasniqi
THIRD CONFERENCE TRACK			
The intended and attained curriculum			
13.20-13.40	10. Digital Competencies in Social Sciences – A Pilot Study. <i>From Design to Practice: Teaching Approaches in the HOMO DIGITALIS Project</i>	Valbona Nathanaïli, Blerta Drenofci (Çani), Konstantinos Giakoumis, Dušanka Bošković, Arbana Kadriu, Anisa Duka	Bujar Gallopeni
13.40-14.00	11. Enhancing Learning through Multimedia Cultural Heritage Applications: Managing Cognitive Load	Merima Muslić, Dušanka Bošković, Vensada Okanović, Selma Rizvić	Blerta Avdia
14.00-14.20	12. Integrating Digital Competencies into Higher Education Curricula. <i>A Case Study from LOGOS University College within the Homo Digitalis Project</i>	Juna Muça, Anxhela Laska, Elpiniqi Merkuri, Edvaldo Begotaraj	Emira Spahaj
14.20-15.40	Lunch		
20.00-22.00	Social Dinner and Awarding of Certificates of Participation and Presentation of Papers		

**PART ONE:
DIGITAL COMPETENCES
IN HIGHER EDUCATION
AND THE LABOUR MARKET**

DEFINING A STRATEGIC ACTION PLAN FOR AI IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Nikolaos AVOURIS

Emeritus Professor, University of Patras, Patras, Greece
avouris@upatras.gr

Abstract

This paper discusses key challenges of Artificial Intelligence in Education, with main focus on higher education institutions. We start with reviewing normative actions of international organizations and concerns expressed about the current technical landscape. Then we proceed with proposing a framework that comprises five key dimensions relating to the main challenges relating to AI in higher education institutions, followed by five key strategic actions that the main stakeholders need to take in order to address the current developments. We map these actions to the main stakeholders of higher education and propose a deployment plan. This defines a framework along the dimensions: Challenges, Actions, Stakeholders, Deployment CASD. Examples of AI specific actions at the institutional and individual course level are also provided and discussed.

Keywords: AI, Higher Education, politics in higher education

ABOUT THE AUTHOR

NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Nikolaos M. Avouris received his diploma in Electrical Engineering from the National Technical University of Athens, Greece, in 1979. He earned his M.Sc. (1981) and Ph.D. (1983) degrees from the University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology (UMIST), U.K. He was a Postdoctoral Researcher at UMIST from 1983 to 1984, an Assistant Professor at the Technical Educational Institute of Athens (1985–1986), a Scientific Officer at the Joint Research Centre (JRC) in Ispra, Italy (1986–1993), and a Software Engineer at the Public Power Corporation (PPC), Athens (1993–1994). In 1994, he joined the University of Patras, Greece, where he served as Associate Professor until 2001, when he was appointed Full Professor of Software Engineering and Human–Computer Interaction (HCI). He is the founder and head of the HCI Group at the University of Patras. His research interests include the design and evaluation of interactive systems, usability engineering, collaboration technologies, context-aware computing systems, and the analysis and evaluation of collaborative activities. Professor Emeritus, University of Patras.

INTRODUCTION

We live in accelerated transformative times in education, as AI is increasingly embedded across all levels and forms of formal and informal learning, like in most aspects of life. Common educational applications of AI include personalized learning, AI tutors, automated assessment and feedback, curriculum design support, support for lifelong learning pathways, management of admissions/ progression decisions and many more. As Kasneci *et al.* (2023) argue, while large language models (LLMs) offer unprecedented support for personalized learning, feedback, and access to knowledge, they also pose complex challenges for academic integrity, transparency, and educational equity. The common practice in most higher education institutions is depicted in the recent Educause Horizon Report (Robert *et al.*, 2025) which confirms the continuous rise of use of AI in universities and outlines the current practice: On one hand, the students are increasingly reported using AI tools like ChatGPT to generate essays, do research, or get help with assignments, while teachers are experimenting with AI-driven lesson planning and assessment. On the other hand, the key stakeholder’s express serious concerns, about academic integrity, and the erosion of original thought, while teachers’ express questions about how to teach critical thinking and writing when AI can play that role effectively.

In the associated faculty survey (Robert *et al.*, 2025), the responses showed that some instructors embrace AI as a learning assistant, guiding students in how to use it ethically, while others design AI-resistant assignments, like oral exams or handwritten essays. Finally, in terms of institutional policies, many universities and schools are rethinking assessment policies and academic integrity rules, while special emphasis is shifting toward AI literacy, that aims at educators helping students learn how to collaborate with AI, not just avoid it. Studies like Vargas-Murillo *et al.* (2023) literature review of GenAI in higher education, highlight that AI is already reshaping academic practices internationally — prompting institutions to develop policies that balance innovation, fairness, and integrity in AI-assisted learning environments.

Fig. 1. Components of the CASD (Challenges, Actions, Stakeholders, Deployment) framework

There have been various attempts and guidelines for policies development, both from international institutions, like UNESCO, EU, etc, and universities associations, like the APRU maturity framework (Liu & Bates, 2025), that reflects the institutional culture, policies, access, familiarity and trust to AI, that determine how to design, implement, and evaluate an AI strategy at institutional level.

In this paper, we review the current literature and proposals by international institutions and researchers to define the main challenges related to AI in Education, next we present, given these challenges, key dimensions of concern followed by a set of key strategic actions to address these concerns and deployment of these actions. Next, we define the framework dimensions, starting from the key challenges of AI. The main components of the proposed framework are shown in Fig. 1, which, illustrates how challenges inform strategic actions that are mapped to stakeholders and implemented through deployment strategies.

NORMATIVE FOUNDATIONS OF AI

We start with identifying the main challenges related to AI. In order to do that, we first review normative frameworks that have been issued by authoritative bodies, concerning design, deployment and governance of AI. A key reference is the widely adopted framework proposed by UNESCO (2021), that is grounded in human rights, inclusion, sustainability, and peace. In particular, this framework outlines four foundational values that may be affected by AI: (i) *Human Rights and Human Dignity*, i.e. AI must not infringe on learners' fundamental rights (e.g, privacy, autonomy, expression). (ii) *Environmental Sustainability* that commands that AI systems should be designed and used in ways that support sustainability, especially relevant for educational technology systems consuming large-scale data and energy, (iii) *Diversity and Inclusiveness*, AI must be inclusive, respecting different languages, cultures, identities, from which stems the need for localization of AI tools to reflect educational and linguistic diversity, and finally (iv) *Living in Peaceful, and Just Societies*, which implies that education should prepare learners to engage critically and ethically with AI in civic life. A value that emphasizes digital literacy, fairness, and social cohesion. Next the UNESCO framework proceeds with proposal of ten key principles, that are actionable ethical rules, based on these fundamental values. The principles, with examples of their implication in the education sector, are:

- *Privacy and Data Protection*, which relates to possible mass collection of student data via e-proctoring or educational technology platforms
- *Fairness and Non-Discrimination*, which concerns algorithmic bias disadvantaging underrepresented student groups, and marginalized languages
- *Proportionality and Do No Harm*, resulting in the principle that AI systems should not cause more harm or risk than necessary to achieve their intended purpose.
- *Safety and Security*, relating to exposure of minors to manipulative or unsafe systems
- *Human Oversight and Determination*, that concerns the danger of teachers losing control over AI tutoring systems
- *Accountability and Responsibility*, that relates to cases of unclear responsibility for automated decisions in learning analytics

- *Transparency and Explainability*, concerning black-box algorithms in grading or recommendation systems
- *Awareness and Literacy*, e.g. cases of students and staff to be unaware of how AI tools work
- *Sustainability*, that relates to overuse of high-resource AI tools that burden IT infrastructure
- *Multi-stakeholder Governance*, that proposes that governance of AI must include diverse stakeholders: educators, students, parents, technologists, policymakers, civil society.

These ten principles consolidate ideas found in many other, similar frameworks or guidelines, like the UNESCO Guidelines for GenAI in education and research (UNESCO, 2023), the Council of Europe Report on AI and Education (Holmes *et al.* 2022), the European Commission Guidelines, a practitioner-oriented resource that aim at promoting the responsible integration of AI and data in education, (European Commission, 2022), and the Unesco report (Miao *et al.*, 2021) with guidelines for policy makers, that translates high-level ethical and strategic frameworks into practical policy considerations specifically for education systems.

THE AI CHALLENGES

Next, summarizing the proposals of the discussed normative frameworks, we define the five challenges that need to be addressed making *Dimension C* of our framework:

- **Challenge C1: *Fairness and Inclusion*.** Artificial intelligence can unintentionally reinforce bias. Whether in grading, tutoring, or content recommendations, AI may reflect existing social inequalities. It can also exclude students whose needs or languages are underrepresented in the data. To ensure AI in education is fair, we must proactively design for inclusion—considering accessibility, multilingual support, and cultural diversity. Fairness isn't just a technical issue; it's an ethical commitment to serve all learners.
- **Challenge C2: *Privacy and data use*.** AI systems rely heavily on data—often personal, often sensitive. In education, this includes student behaviour, assessment patterns, even emotional states. Without robust protections, AI tools can compromise privacy and data sovereignty. We must ensure that students and teachers are not merely data sources, but informed participants.
- **Challenge C3: *Transparency and Agency*.** It is known that many AI systems operate as black boxes. They offer recommendations or assessments, but their reasoning is obscure—even to the educators using them. This undermines trust and can erode the autonomy of both students and teachers. Transparency is essential: educators should understand how tools work, and students should retain control over their learning. AI must support - not replace - human judgment and critical thinking.
- **Challenge C4: *Accountability and Responsibility*.** When the AI system misjudges a student's answer or gives biased feedback, the question raises who is responsible? Without clear accountability, these errors go unchecked. Institutions must ensure that AI use in education is supervised, auditable, and ultimately human-led. Ethical use requires

human oversight, clear escalation paths, and shared responsibility between developers, educators, and administrators.

- **Challenge C5: *Academic Integrity*.** This challenge is not explicitly present in the normative frameworks, yet it is the main concern of stakeholders, as discussed in Robert *et al.*, (2025), as it touches on many ethical principles of AI. Current AI tools like Large Language Models chatbots pose new questions about originality, authorship, and fairness in education. We need to rethink integrity, not just as enforcement, but as empowerment: teaching students to use AI responsibly, reflecting on how it's used, and designing assignments that reward genuine thinking.

In the next section we proceed with proposing a set of strategic actions to address the discussed here challenges.

THE STRATEGIC ACTIONS

Many proposals have been made for actions to be taken to address the challenges of AI in education. For instance, European Commission (2022) and UNESCO (2021b) contain such ideas. Chan (2023) and Chan & Colloton (2024) have made comprehensive proposals for a policy education framework for university teaching and learning. At the level of institutional policies, there have been many publications reviewing specific countries or compare policies across areas. The review of Dell'Erba *et al.* (2025) concerns the policy documents of top-ranked universities, focusing on the innovation-regulation tension, while Jin *et al.* (2025) analyse adoption of GenAI policies in 40 universities across six global regions focusing on the characteristics of the institutions, like compatibility, trialability, observability, and the communication roles/responsibilities, using innovation diffusion theoretical framework. Finally studies in specific countries reveal the characteristics of their educational systems. Abir & Zhou (2025) who studied Japanese universities, found out their cautious stance toward GenAI, emphasizing concerns about academic integrity, transparency, and unintended misuse, while Li *et al.* (2025) performed a cross-national comparative study involving over 100 policy documents across the US, Japan and China. Using these findings, they developed the UPDF-GAI model for guiding universities in developing AI policies. It is interesting to observe that from this study, the different orientation of different academic systems emerged, with the US leaning toward faculty autonomy, Japan emphasizing government-regulated frameworks, and China generally aligned with a centralized, top-down model, prioritizing AI integration and technology-driven implementation over early-stage policy structuring. Based on these ideas, we provide here a set of key strategic actions, defining the *Action Dimension* of our framework.

- **Action 1: *Revise Curriculum*.** We need to make drastic changes to the curricula content, in order to teach learners how to critically analyse information and verify their sources and develop digital literacy skills that can help them better understand how AI technologies work and how to use them responsibly, this needs to be adapted to the requirements of each subject matter.

- *Action 2: Reform Pedagogy.* The way we teach should be adapted in the times of AI. Emphasis should be given on assignments and assessments conducted in class, so that the use of AI for solving problems and completing assignments can be monitored and the unfair use of AI can be avoided.
- *Action 3: Training of Educators.* We need to design training programs for educators so that they can better understand AI technologies and effectively integrate their capabilities into the educational process.
- *Action 4: Support Local Content.* We need to ensure that the AI models used in education can be properly trained in the local language and with local data, by providing high-quality, machine-readable local content. An interesting relevant observation is that the corpora used for training AI models, have often bias in certain languages and cultures. For instance, the OSCAR23¹ corpus, a large-scale, multilingual text dataset, with around 1 trillion words, derived from the Common Crawl web archive, used for training many AI models, contains 48% of content in English, and just 0.71% in Greek, or 0.04% in Albanian, while some minority languages are not existent.
- *Action 5: Establish Policy and Governance.* Educational institutions must establish clear regulations regarding the use of AI technologies, defining what is permitted and what is not, as well as the consequences of related violations of academic integrity.

It is obvious from the list of these strategic actions that these responses require participation of different stakeholders of the higher education ecosystem. In the next section we will discuss the role of the five key stakeholders in these actions.

THE ROLES OF STAKEHOLDERS

We consider the following five key stakeholders of the higher education ecosystem: the Students, Educators, Institutions, Policymakers and Technology providers. We will briefly describe next their roles in the proposed strategic actions.

- *S1. Students.* These are the main stakeholders as they are the target of the main mission of the higher education system. They participate as receivers of the new services. They are affected by *Revised Curriculum*, as through this action's results they gain AI literacy and awareness of ethical use, by *Reformed Pedagogy*, as they experience new ways of teaching, for instance, more inclusive, AI-aware assessments and by *Support Local Content*, as they have, as a result, access to AI tools relevant to their language and culture.
- *S2. Educators.* The faculty of higher education need to adapt to the new conditions, participating actively in all proposed strategic actions, In *Revised Curriculum*, they are asked to teach new topics encouraging critical thinking and AI literacy. For *Reform Pedagogy*, they need to adapt their teaching using new AI-resilient assessment, In *Train Educators*, to participate in faculty training actions to acquire competence to use and explain AI tools, in *Support Local Content* to teach using culturally appropriate and multilingual tools, and in *Policy & Governance*, to implement the AI policies of the institutions.

³ <https://oscar-project.github.io/documentation/versions/oscar-2301/>

- *S3. Institutions.* The higher education institutions are asked to play a key role according to the proposed framework. For *Revise Curriculum* They need to develop curricula that align with digital competencies and AI use, for *Reform Pedagogy*, they need to encourage pedagogy that includes fairer evaluation methods, for *Train Educators*, to provide training programs and support systems for their faculty, in *Support Local Content*, to invest in open educational resources and local repositories, and in *Policy & Governance*, to establish oversight and internal governance structures.
- *S4. Policy Makers.* These are institutions at the national level (e.g. Ministries of Education) or international level (e.g. EU, UNESCO, etc.). There are already recommendations for policies, as discussed in previous section, while the EU in its AI Act makes explicit reference to the education sector as a high-risk domain with obligations for technology providers and for institutions. However, there are not explicit policies in most parts of the world. The role of the policy making bodies is crucial. In *Revise Curriculum*, the policies should contain curriculum guidelines that include AI ethics and AI literacy, for *Reform Pedagogy*, policies should exist that encourage compliance with national and international standards for ethical AI based pedagogy. For *Train Educators*, there should be funding and policies that mandate teacher training on AI, for *Support Local Content*, policies that ensure content diversity and inclusion, with local language and culture. *Policy & Governance*, there should regulate all aspects of development and use of AI in education, based on ethical frameworks.
- *S5. Technology Providers.* The responsibilities of the AI technology providers are high according to the normative recommendations and the existing legal framework, e.g. the EU AI Act, foresee that the developers of the technology bear most of the legal burden relating to compliance, documentation and risk management. In the frame of *Reform Pedagogy*, they are required to develop technologies supporting ethical and creative pedagogy, for *Support Local Content*, they are required to localize the developed AI systems for underrepresented languages or contexts, and for *Policy & Governance*, they need to take all necessary actions to comply with standards; ensure ethical, transparent, equitable technologies.

Having outlined the strategic actions and their mapping to key stakeholders, we now turn to the question of how this framework can be implemented effectively in institutional settings.

FRAMEWORK DEPLOYMENT

As discussed in the previous sections, the proposed here framework requires the active involvement of all key stakeholders of the higher education ecosystem. Given that the technological ground of AI is in continuous evolution, a deployment of such framework needs on one hand, to be flexible to accommodate this shifting technological background, and on the other hand, to match the readiness and the culture of the specific institution or educational system. Liu & Bates (2025) identify five important dimensions, that make up the CRAFT framework for AI strategy implementation in a higher education institution:

Culture, Rules, Access, Familiarity, Trust. These dimensions relate to alignment of the AI strategy with institutional mission, pedagogical values, and change-readiness (the *Culture* dimension), to definition of rules that provide the governance layer: ethical guidelines, acceptable use policies, and accountability structures, to ensure equitable access to AI tools to training, and infrastructure across all stakeholders (the *Rules* dimension), to build AI literacy, technical skills, as well as critical, ethical, and creative competences (the *Familiarity* dimension), and finally the *Trust* dimension, that facilitates transparency, dialogue, and confidence in institutional strategy and tools. This leads to a roadmap for deployment of AI policies, following a sequence of steps:

- Start with Culture, by surveying faculty/ student values, identify champions, and establish how ready the institution is for establishing these policies,
- develop the Rules through outlined actions, like co-creation of policies on ethical use of AI, especially in assessment (guidelines for pedagogy reform and new curricula),
- next, there is need to ensure access, this is done by deploying institutionally supported AI tools, while special measures have to be providing in ensuring language/inclusive access,
- then build familiarity, i.e. to offer cross-disciplinary AI literacy programs; empower staff (teacher training action), and
- finally, in order to establish trust, there is need to share data about AI use outcomes; and invite ongoing community input.

Furthermore, Chan & Colloton (2024), provide guidelines to enhance the deployment framework: As a starting point, they focus on changing institutional culture, from awareness of AI's educational implications to proactive leadership engagement and identification of faculty champions, role-based responsibilities, feedback mechanisms, and aligning AI strategy with institutional mission. They also provide a policy blueprint for institutional AI guidelines, including templates for acceptable use, ethical standards, and operational processes, while they advocate an iterative, inclusive design process with experts, faculties, librarians, disability services, and IT teams participating in co-design.

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

In this paper we have reviewed normative approaches to AI in education and outlined a framework for design and deployment of policies for higher education. Concluding this review, we provide some references to resources that can help with implementing the proposed action plan. First at the level of individual courses, there are various examples. Stanford Teaching Commons (2023) provide templates to instructors through an AI Teaching guide, with specific guidelines on course AI policies, AI-resistant assignments, and support for AI literacy. Avouris *et al.* (2025) have described the experience of re-design of a computer science course in order to be AI-resilient, providing examples on re-design of assessment strategies, pedagogy and learning objectives of the course, while Chan & Colloton (2024) propose strategies for redesigning assignments and evaluation, the *Six assessment redesign pivotal strategies*.

In conclusion, as AI technologies continue to evolve, higher education institutions must adopt dynamic, inclusive, and ethically grounded strategies. The proposed framework offers a foundation for such action, yet ongoing collaboration between educators, students, policymakers, and developers remains essential. We should however consider the risks and barriers of the strategic framework, like institutional resistance, funding, faculty disposition, that may affect its implementation. Future work should focus on evaluating institutional readiness, piloting policy innovations, and fostering global exchange of good practices in AI-enhanced education. Frameworks like the DigiReady+ (Chounta *et al.* 2024), that measure digital readiness of higher education institutions can be useful tools in supporting this process.

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INSTITUTIONAL POLICIES AND STRATEGIC DIRECTIONS FOR ADVANCING DIGITAL COMPETENCIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Hajdin BERISHA,^{1*} Agron HAJDARI,¹
Bekim SAMADRAXHA²

¹Public International Business College Mitrovica

²Department of Higher Education, Ministry of Education, Science,
Technology and Innovation
The Republic of Kosovo

Corresponding Author*: h.berisha@ibcmitrovica.eu

Abstract

The rapid evolution of digital technologies is reshaping the landscape of higher education and demanding institutions to align their policies and practices with the skills required for a knowledge-based economy. Within the Kosovo higher education system, fostering digital competencies has emerged as a strategic priority to enhance teaching, learning, research, and graduate employability. This paper explores how institutional policies, and strategic directions can drive the systematic development of digital skills in higher education. It examines the current policy frameworks, highlights key challenges and identifies opportunities for further advancement. The study emphasizes the need for coherent governance, inclusive digital transformation, and sustainable investment to ensure higher education institutions can adapt to technology trends. Ultimately, the paper argues that advancing digital competencies is not only a technological imperative but also a strategic enabler for quality, equity, and international competitiveness in Kosovo's higher education system.

Keywords: Higher education, technology, policies, strategy.

INDEX OF AUTHORS AND PAPER NUMBERS

Abazi-Bexheti, Lejla, 6
Avdia, Blerta, 1
Avouris, Nikolaos, 8
Begotaraj, Edvaldo, 12
Berisha, Hajdin, 9
Bošković, Dušanka, 10, 11
Ciba, Sara, 4
Drenofci (Çani), Blerta, 2, 10
Duka, Anisa, 10
Duka, Ardis, 4
Giakoumis, Konstantinos, 10
Gjoka, Ajla, 4
Gjoni, Migena, 4
Hajdari, Agron, 9
Hasalla, Gertjana, 3
Haska, Lumturi, 4
Hysa, Malvina, 1
Kadriu, Arbana, 6, 10
Kyriatsis, Panagiotis, 4
Laska, Anxhela, 12
Mazari, Romir, 4
Mena, Edisela, 1
Merkuri, Elpiniqi, 12
Minxuri, Dorina, 5
Muça, Juna, 12
Muslić, Merima, 10
Nathanaili, Valbona, 2, 10
Okanović, Vensada, 10
Papadhopulli, Fulvio, 7
Rizvić, Selma, 10
Samadraxha, Bekim, 9
Spahaj, Emira, 1
Tafaj, Megi, 7
Vesho, Nikolla, 4

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The responsible use of Artificial Intelligence is essential for fostering innovation and advancing digital competencies in higher education.

PROF. ILIA NINKA

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education is about more than technology. It is about developing university-level strategies and adequate national and regional policies to support digital transformation. Albanian Higher Education Institutions have not yet developed an ethical framework for the use of ChatGPT and similar AI applications.

DR. VALBONA NATHANAILI

The use of Artificial Intelligence in higher education it is aligning universities with the labour market and forging strong partnerships between higher education institutions and employers.

DR. KETI HOXHA

Digital transformation is no longer a future aspiration. It is a current imperative.

PROF. DUŠANKA BOŠKOVIC

... with vision, with cooperation, and with determination, we can ensure that AI serves not just technology, but learning. Not just efficiency, but wisdom.

PROF. NIKOLAOS AVOURIS

Altogether, the case-studies in this volume trace a roadmap for higher education in the Western Balkans that amalgamates tradition and innovation, strives to pursue equitable access to digital opportunities, and positions regional universities as active contributors to Europe's wider digital transformation.

PROF. KONSTANTINOS GLAKOUMIS

info@kulogos.edu.al

